

Improving energy efficiency in seafood freezing with brine technology

Eirik Starheim SVENDSEN^{*(a)}, Erlend INDERGÅRD^(a), Jan BENGSCHE^(a), Kristina Norne WIDELL^(a), Lukas KÖSTER^(a), Tom Ståle NORDTVEDT^(a)

^(a) SINTEF Ocean

Trondheim, 7465, Trondheim, Norway

*Corresponding author: eirik.starheim.svendsen@sintef.no

ABSTRACT

Seafood is an important source of the world's food supply and demand is growing. More and more seafood is being sold frozen, which extends the shelf life and creates more sustainable transportation options. Depending on the type of product, different freezing methods and equipment are used with a great variation in energy intensity. Brine freezing, with its good heat transfer properties, is one method that can improve the energy efficiency of this process but is not widely used. This paper explores the implications of introducing brine freezing into different seafood production chains, focused on potential reductions in energy consumption, quality attributes and practical aspects. A particular focus is placed on brine freezing of mackerel as part of a two-stage freezing process, including results from preliminary trials that show rapid freezing times but also revealed some practical barriers.

Keywords: freezing, brine, sustainability, energy efficiency, pelagic fish

1. INTRODUCTION

Freezing of seafood is an important method to extend shelf life and there is a variety of freezing methods employed in the seafood industry today. In simple terms, one could say that there are three basic methods: air blasting, contact freezing and immersion freezing. The subject of this paper, brine freezing, falls into the latter category. Brine freezing is a method that is not widely used in the Norwegian seafood industry (except for freezing of crabs), but in the early 1900s the method was hailed as modern (Svendsen et al., 2022) and several different methods were patented. In particular, Nekolai Dahl's method was widely used in Norway and other countries, and consisted of sprinkling a brine of ice and salts over perforated transport boxes filled with fish (Holst and Notevarp, 1932). As advancements were made in air blast and contact freezing, the use of brine ebbed out. A key motivation to (again) look into brine freezing is that the method can be very energy efficient and very rapid. There are two reasons for the increase in energy efficiency: by immersing in liquid, you usually get a great contact with the entire food surface, and liquids are great conductors of heat (compared to air) which leads to a large heat transfer coefficient (HTC). According to James & James (2014), the HTC for immersion in agitated liquids is around 500 W/m²K, plate freezing 450 W/m²K and air (6 m/s) is about 60 W/m²K. Another aspect of brine freezing is that it typically employs higher freezing media temperatures compared to both air blasting and plate freezing. While the evaporation temperature of the refrigerator serving cold to an air or plate freezer might be relatively low, i.e. -40 °C, a brine solution (NaCl) has an eutectic point of -21 °C and thus the evaporator can be operated at higher suction pressure. There are also some downsides to the method which limits its range of applications, mainly due to potential quality shifts in food due to salt uptake (Kauffeld, 2005) and corrosion in equipment due to brine spillage (Magnussen et al., 2008). The motivation behind this study is to unlock the energy efficiency potential of brine freezing for various applications in the seafood industry, and has been carried out within the scope of the EU Horizon 2020 project ENOUGH.

2. APPLICATIONS OF BRINE FREEZING

As stated in the introduction, brine freezing is not widely used today with exception for freezing of crabs. The method has however in the latter years received some attention, and this section is a brief review on the different applications that have been investigated.

2.1. Brine freezing of whitefish

Frozen headed and gutted (H/G) whitefish is one of the primary sources for fillet and clipfish production in Norway. The fish, mainly cod (*Gadus morhua*), but also saithe (*Pollachius virens*) and haddock (*Melanogrammus aeglefinus*), is usually frozen onboard large ocean-going trawlers using vertical plate freezers, producing 25 or 50 kg fish blocks that are packed in bags and stacked on pallets. The first step of on-shore-processing is then to thaw the blocks in tanks with circulating seawater, which can be a slow process due to the low surface area-to-volume ratio. Single freezing the fish in brine could lead to a more controlled thawing, which in turn could increase the yield (Haugland, 2002). This was investigated by Larsen et al. (2022), who compared brine freezing of cod, saithe and haddock against the traditional plate freezing method, which after a 6-month storage period was thawed and either went to fillet production or clipfish production. They found that the freezing rate in brine (NaCl 23%, -22°C) was about 63-73 min/kg, where the leanest fish (haddock, cod) took the longest time, and that the shape of the fish is maintained. After thawing they found no significant difference in thawing losses (0-41-2.09%) but noted that brine frozen fish had less visible blood in cut-regions and that haddock had a significant firmer texture compared to plate frozen. They also noticed yellow discolouration in the cut-regions, which was not an issue for fillet production (i.e., these areas removed) but for clipfish production has an impact on market acceptance. With respect to energy use for the different freezing methods, they theoretically evaluated that brine freezing had a specific energy consumption (SEC) of 0.08 kWh/kg, while the figures were 0.115 and 0.15 kWh/kg for plate freezing and tunnel freezing, respectively.

Stormo et al. (2021) investigated freezing of gutted and filleted haddock products, using a purpose-built brine freezer (NaCl, 23%, operating at -18 to -20 °C) and air blasting (-30 °C cold storage w/powerful fan). When comparing freezing rates, they concluded that the brine freezing was 2-3 times faster than air freezing (dependent on fish size). They saw that the freezing rate slowed down as the core temperature approached the brine temperature, and thus freezing should be stopped at around -15 °C. When they increased the circulation rate from 0.075 to 0.18 m/s, they saw that freezing time could be reduced by 30-37%.

Both studies commented on salt uptake which is expected when exposing fish to a salt brine. However, Stormo et al. (2021) remarked that for gutted haddock the skin acts as a barrier, and when subsequently thawed in water no significant difference in salt content of the muscle could be measured. Filleted products however don't have this natural barrier, but the rapid freezing creates a shell which partially protects against salt uptake. The salt content of the surface layer was found to be high, but it was possible to reduce this by thawing in fresh water (unless surface was too dry). Larsen et al. (2022) measured the salt content in the muscle of cod, and found a significant difference between brine and plate freezing (0.19 g/100g higher for brine frozen cod), but results from the following taste panel (of clipfish) did not show any significant difference in salt taste between the treatments.

2.2. Brine freezing of pelagic fish

Most of the pelagic fish (90% of total volume) (mackerel (*Scomber scombrus*), herring (*Clupea harengus*)) that is caught and landed in Norway is exported, and about 95% of the exported volume is frozen round (Directorate of Fisheries, 2023; Norwegian Seafood Council, 2023). To strengthen the Norwegian pelagic industry, there have been some initiatives to increase the degree of processing before export, and to transition from season-only to year-round operation of pelagic processing plants. Østvik et al. (2018) looked into utilizing brine freezing for this concept, covering a variety of different aspects. From type of salt brine (NaCl, MgCl₂, CaCl₂), freezing of packed and unpacked, single-freezing or batch-freezing, and did so using both a lab-scale brine freezing rig (batch) and a continuous brine freezing rig installed at a pelagic fish processing plant. During the first set of trials, they concluded that single freezing of mackerel followed by

packaging in NaCl-brine (23.6%, -20 °C) was the most feasible approach. Freezing rates were recorded between 2.5-4.6 min/°C dependent on weight (300-600 gr) when frozen to -18 °C in the lab-scale rig. For the continuous rig, they achieved a production rate between 450-700 kg/hour, freezing from an initial core temperature of 3-4 °C to -14.7 - -17.8 °C in 55 minutes. During the latter trial they also measured the energy consumption (of the refrigeration compressor and brine circulation pump) and found that during steady state production the drawn power was about 33 kW, giving a SEC of 0.054 kWh/kg. The frozen mackerel was thawed after 3 months of storage, and sensory evaluation showed that brine frozen raw fish (round, filleted) had slightly better scores (but not significantly) than tunnel frozen. The most apparent difference was that brine frozen fish retained its natural, straight shape much better than tunnel frozen which is important for the filleting process.

Oxidation of fatty fish can result in development of off-flavours and odours, i.e., rancid smell and taste. Early reports on brine freezing have stated that brine freezing can accelerate this undesired effect in herring (Lorentzen, 1958) and for mackerel and horse mackerel (*Trachurus trachurus*) (Aubourg and Gallardo, 2005). The latter found by sensory evaluation that brine frozen mackerel received rejection scores after 5 months of frozen storage, due to odour, colour and general aspect. Larssen et al. (2020) conducted a 24-month long storage study, investigating oxidation in mackerel that was brine frozen and tunnel frozen. In contrast to previous studies, they found no significant differences in development between the groups when measuring free fatty content (FFA), TBARS-values or peroxide values. At the end of the storage period, a sensory evaluation gave no significant differences, except for the straighter shape of the brine frozen mackerel.

3. METHODS: BRINE FREEZING TRIALS IN THE ENOUGH PROJECT

One key objective of the ENOUGH project (EU H2020, number 101036588) is to promote and test technology that could reduce the emissions related to food production, and one of the demonstrators is focused on brine freezing of seafood due to its potential to increase energy efficiency. This section will cover the activities related to this demonstrator and includes results from the trials that have been conducted so far. The heart of the demonstrator is a purpose-built brine freezer system (Fig. 1), consisting of a tank (0.91m x 3.0m x 1.0m) in which brine is circulated and agitated, assisted by a Bock semi-hermetic compressor with nominal cooling capacity of 47 kW at -25/+30 °C. Practical operation limit of the NaCl-brine with this setup was -14 °C, albeit the eutectic point is as low as -22 °C. For some of the trials, other relevant equipment such as complete pelagic packing line etc. was used.

3.1. Two-stage freezing of mackerel

One of potential applications of brine freezing is in the pelagic fish processing industry. Most of the pelagic fish (i.e., mackerel and herring) that is caught and landed in Norway is frozen round in 20 kg cardboard boxes and exported. The freezing is then typically done in large freezing tunnels, where the boxes are stacked on trays and frozen within 18-22 hours. The two-stage freezing concept consists of single freezing mackerel in the first stage using brine to extract as much heat as possible, before packing and completing the freezing cycle in a tunnel. This can save time spent in the tunnels significantly, and therefore also reduce energy consumption and increase production capacity. A critical parameter of the processing is that one should be able to pack 20 kg of frozen fish within a standard cardboard box, which limits how much heat can be extracted during the first stage due to stiffness. Østvik et al. (2018) reported that only 13-14 kg of mackerel would fit into a standard cardboard box due to stiffness. So far 2 trials have been carried out for this concept, where the objective of the first trial was to find the 'sweet spot', i.e. how much heat could be extracted from the mackerel while maintaining flexibility. Objective of the second trial was to run a complete two-stage freezing cycle to see how much time-reduction one could achieve in the tunnels.

Figure 1: The brine freezer rig used for the trials

1st trial: 50 kg of mackerel was frozen using a salt brine (NaCl, 23%) at -14 °C. 5 mackerels were instrumented with temperature loggers (iButton DS1922I, acc. ±0.5 °C) at 3 locations: core, skin and core of the tail. The batch was allowed to freeze completely, and then transferred to thawing in a 1000 L bin with circulating fresh water (appr. 9.5 °C). Samples were taken out at different tail temperatures to measure the flexibility using a custom-made protractor disc. To assess the flexibility, a practical evaluation was subsequently carried out using the pelagic packing line to verify if packing into boxes was possible.

2nd trial: 20 kg of mackerel was brine-frozen aiming for target temperatures resulted from the 1st trial, packed and transported to a nearby pelagic processor where the freezing cycle was completed. The box was stacked together with ordinary production volume (i.e., fresh mackerel) on a tray, and temperatures was measured for both groups.

Theoretical energy evaluation: There was no logging of the energy consumption during the trials, but a theoretical evaluation of how much energy can be saved due to reduced holding time in air tunnels has been carried out. Data, both measured and simulated, for batch freezing of fish in air freezing tunnels have been used from previous work (Widell, 2012; Widell et al., 2014, 2012). In short, the total heat load in a tunnel can be attributed to the products (65%), fans (30%) and others (5%, transmission losses, defrosting etc.). In particular, the heat added by the fans account for a large share which the refrigeration system must remove, thus increasing the necessary work to drive the refrigeration system, in addition to driving the fans themselves. This means that by shortening the holding time in a tunnel, significant energy savings can be made. Estimation of energy use for the brine freezing stage was based on empirical numbers from Østvik et al. (2018) (see 2.2 Brine freezing of pelagic fish). For tunnel freezing calculations, heat loads were calculated using data series mentioned above by numerical integration (trapezoidal rule using MS Excel). Work of the refrigeration compressor was then calculated by:

$$W_{comp} = \frac{Q}{COP} [kWh] \quad 1$$

Total work is then work of the compressor and fans:

$$W_{tot} = W_{comp} + W_{fans} [kWh] \quad 2$$

Where W_{fans} is assumed equal to the heat load they add ($W_{fans} = Q_{fans}$).

3.2. Brine freezing of salmon

Another potential application is freezing salmon products in brine, either portioned, round, packed or unpacked. Norway holds the position as the primary producer of farmed Atlantic salmon, annually exporting approximately 1-1.2 million tonnes, with the majority (~90%) being fresh (Norwegian Seafood Council, 2023). Filleted (and portioned) products are usually vacuum-packed and frozen individually (or 4x4-linked packaging) employing air-based IQF freezers. Such equipment is very efficient with respect to freezing time, but as for other air freezing equipment, a significant share of the heat load and energy consumption is due to air fans. Whole salmon is typically single-frozen in tunnels, unpacked and placed on specially designed trays with the gutted belly facing upwards, albeit some producers also use gyro freezers for whole salmon as well. Two trials have been carried out on salmon in this demonstrator so far, freezing of vacuum-packed portions and freezing of whole salmon in salt brine (NaCl, 23%, -14 °C). The main objective of these trials was to investigate freezing rates, but also to observe for any potential changes in sensorial quality attributes.

1st trial: 6 portions were made out from fresh salmon fillets, each weighing roughly 300 gr with a maximum thickness of 30 mm, instrumented with temperature loggers in the core and skin (iButton DS1922I) and vacuum-packed. The portions were then fixed to perforated boxes and immersed in the circulating brine until completely frozen.

2nd trial: 4 gutted salmons were used for this trial, of which 2 were vacuum-packed. Temperature sensors were placed in the core and skin (iButtons for vacuum-packed; thermowire type K for unpacked). The salmons were placed in the circulating brine (NaCl, 23%, -14 °C) and frozen overnight.

4. RESULTS FROM THE TRIALS

4.1. Two-stage freezing of mackerel – 1st trial

The temperature development during freezing and thawing in one of the instrumented mackerels is shown in Fig. 2. The holding time in the brine was about 160 minutes, by which time the core temperature had almost reached the temperature of the brine, i.e., -14 °C (this was also the case for the other samples, except one sample which reached -14 °C in 115 minutes due to small size). The tail can be seen to freeze at a much faster rate, with a rapid ice crystallisation phase (10–20-minute mark) before the rate again accelerates and reaches -14 °C in 80-90 minutes. This was expected, as the tail section is a thinner part compared to where the geometric core is. However, this also means that the undesired stiffness occurs at a much greater rate than we can extract heat, and thus impacts how the concept can be optimised. Also note the rather slow freezing rate at the surface: this is due to the loggers being placed under the skin.

Figure 2: Temperature development in one mackerel (core, tail and skin) during freezing and thawing

After freezing, the batch of mackerel was put to thaw in a 1000 L bin filled with water at 9.5 °C, which can be seen around the 160-minute-mark. Yet again we see the influence of each sections size, i.e., the tail is thawing at a more rapid rate compared to the core. After 10 minutes of thawing, temperature in the tail has increased by 7 °C while core temperature was raised by 3 °C. During this period, samples were taken out at different intervals to measure the stiffness. Two examples are shown in Fig. 3, where the left picture shows stiffness when the tail temperature was -5°C.

Figure 3: Measuring stiffness in mackerel. Left: tail temperature -5°C. Right: tail temperature -2.7°C.

The right-hand picture in Fig. 3 shows a mackerel that during packaging tests was deemed flexible enough to fit 20 kg within a box, and this degree of flexibility was recorded at a tail temperature of -2.7 °C. At the same time, the core temperature was recorded at about -5.6 °C. The trial concluded with these temperature levels as target temperatures for subsequent trials.

4.2. Two-stage freezing of mackerel – 2nd trial

After the target temperatures was identified in the 1st trial, purpose of the 2nd trial was to brine-freeze a batch of mackerel and then complete the freezing in tunnels. Target temperatures was achieved during the first stage, but due to logistic issues transporting the batch to the nearby pelagic plant, there was a 3-hour-hold up which resulted in the core temperature increasing to -2.8 °C. The temperature development of the brine-frozen box, and a box with fresh mackerel (control) is shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4: Temperature development in 20 kg cardboard boxes of mackerel during tunnel freezing, brine-frozen and fresh

This most likely affected the results, but they still show the effect of pre-freezing on required holding time in the tunnels: -18 °C was reached in the brine-frozen box (center) after 12.8 hours in the tunnel, while the fresh box took 16.5 hours. Also, the temperature sensor in the fresh box was located near the surface of the lid, i.e., it can be assumed that the center temperature was higher.

4.3. Two-stage freezing of mackerel – theoretical energy evaluation

Measured and simulated data as described in section 3.1 was used for theoretical evaluation and is shown in Fig. 5. The temperature curve is a previous measurement for a box of mackerels from Widell (2012), the product load is based on simulations carried out by Widell et al. (2012), while the heat load attributed to fans and others is based on Widell et al. (2014), i.e., 30% and 5% of the total heat load, respectively.

Figure 5: Data used for theoretical evaluation

Assuming 100 tonnes of mackerel, then the total heat load can be found by integration: 9627 kWh. Energy required to drive the fans is 2888 kWh (W_{fans}), and it's assumed that this is converted to heat which the refrigeration system must remove. With a COP of 2, the total energy input found by Eq. 1 and Eq. 2 is 7701 kWh, or a SEC of 77 kWh/tonne. Note that this is a very low figure compared to previous studies: Widell et al. (2022) found in an energy analysis of a pelagic processing plant that the annual SEC ranged between 200-247 kWh/tonne based on measurements for an entire plant; Dale (2006) found a SEC of 120-135 kWh/tonne based on measurements specific for freezing tunnels.

Starting the tunnel freezing stage when the core temperature is -5°C , then going by the figure we reduce the freezing time from 20 to 10 hours. This reduces the heat load and power input to the fans by 50%, or 1444 kWh. In theory, this should reduce the power input to the refrigeration system by 722 kW, or a total energy saving of 2166 kWh/100 tonne batch. Going by the results achieved by Østvik et al. (2018), we can recalculate the SEC for brine freezing mackerel towards -5°C to 30.6 kWh/tonne, i.e., it requires a total 3056 kWh of energy for the first stage. The total energy consumption for the two-stage freezing is then 6631 kWh, or a saving of about 14%. Of course, these numbers are theoretical and only accounts for energy used to drive the freezing processes, and thus needs to be assessed and measured in further work.

4.4. Brine freezing of salmon – 1st trial

Temperature development for 4 of the 6 salmon portions frozen in brine is shown in Fig. 6 (two samples excluded due to faulty data). It took about 43-51 minutes for all samples to freeze from a temperature of 2.5°C to -10°C , at which point the freezing rate slows down and it would be practical to complete freezing in another manner. The variation can be explained by slight differences in sample sizes and placement of loggers. This rate was deemed as slower compared to the methods currently employed today.

Figure 6: Temperature development for brine-frozen salmon portions

It was observed that the freezing affected the colour, i.e., the samples went from a deep, orange hue to a lighter and more pale orange, as shown in Fig. 7. This phenomena has been previously described and studied by Ottestad et al. (2011), who explains that colour-change occurs as an effect of freezing rate. A fast freezing rate employing low temperatures motivates the growth of small ice crystals, that in turn leads to higher light scattering. This is a purely visual function, nevertheless assumed important for the consumer acceptance, and it reverses when the food is thawed, which was observed in this trial as well.

Figure 7: One of the samples, before (left) and after freezing

4.5. Brine freezing of salmon – 2nd trial

Temperature sensors failed for the two unpacked salmons in the 2nd trial, i.e. only temperature development for the vacuum-packed salmons is shown in Fig. 8. The figure also shows measurements from a previous study, where salmon was single frozen in tunnels (i.e., conventional method) (Nordtvedt et al., 2003). Air distribution in tunnels is an important factor affecting the freezing rate, and products placed at different locations will experience different conditions. Therefore, this data is divided into 2 groups by location: near air inlet ('best' condition) and near air outlet.

Figure 8: Core temperature development for whole salmon in brine freezing rig, overlaid on previous measurements of salmon freezing in tunnels

The freezing rates obtained in the brine trial is in line with the fastest rates observed for tunnel freezing, but obviously by using a brine at $-14\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ the rate slows down around $-10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. As seen previously, it's possible to operate a NaCl-brine as low as $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in practical operation, but one would likely expect a similar slow rate when the product reaches the brine temperature in those conditions. To further build on this approach, one could either go the route of two-stage freezing, i.e., pre-freezing salmon in brine and completing the freezing cycle in tunnels, similar to the two-stage freezing of mackerel concept. Or one could look into using other brines, either MgCl_2 or CaCl_2 , which when saturated have eutectic points at $-33.6\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $-55\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, respectively.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has covered recent research in brine freezing of seafood and found that there have been a renewed interest in employing this method, mostly due to the promising energy efficiency the method entails. In recent years, there have been projects and studies focused on whitefish (cod, haddock) and on mackerel, showing promising results with respect to practical feasibility of the technology. For some products however, the salt uptake might be a problem, while there are contradicting results with respect to oxidation of fatty fish. Furthermore, as a demonstrator in the ENOUGH project, a brine freezing rig has been used to conduct several small-scale trials of different applications. For brine freezing of mackerel, a two-stage freezing concept has been described and tested with promising results. The concept shows that for the fish to be flexible enough to fit 20 kg in a standard cardboard box, the mackerel must be frozen-thawed in brine before frozen completely in a tunnel. A theoretical energy evaluation showed that the energy savings for this concept was 14% compared to only using air tunnels. Brine freezing of salmon also shows rapid freezing rates, albeit for portions the conventional methods are probably faster. However, since these methods are based on air blasting, there is a potential for reducing energy demand.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The activity described in this manuscript has been performed within the project ENOUGH. ENOUGH has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036588.

REFERENCES

- Aubourg, S.P., Gallardo, J.M., 2005. Effect of brine freezing on the rancidity development during the frozen storage of small pelagic fish species. *Eur. Food Res. Technol.* 220, 107–112. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00217-004-1024-0>
- Dale, Ø., 2006. Pelagisk industri - Studie for muligheter med dagens teknologi (Project report). COWI AS.
- Directorate of Fisheries, 2023. Fangst fordelt på art [WWW Document]. *Catch Data Nor.* URL <https://www.fiskeridir.no/Yrkesfiske/Tall-og-analyse/Fangst-og-kvoter/Fangst/Fangst-fordelt-paa-art> (accessed 12.15.23).
- Emblem Larssen, W., Barnung, T., Bjørkevoll, I., 2022. Lakefrysing av hvitfisk (No. 2203). Møreforskning.
- Haugland, A., 2002. Industrial Thawing of Fish - to improve quality, yield and capacity. PhD Thesis Nor. Univ. Sci. Technol.
- Holst, A., Notevarp, O., 1932. Om frysning av fisk og fiskefilet.
- James, S.J., James, C., 2014. Chilling and Freezing of Foods, in: Clark, S., Jung, S., Lamsal, B. (Eds.), *Food Processing*. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, Chichester, UK, pp. 79–105. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118846315.ch5>
- Kauffeld, M., 2005. Direct Contact Chilling and Freezing of Foods in Ice Slurries. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28391.68009>
- Larssen, W.E., Fylling, T., Hellebø, A., Bjørkevoll, I., Barnung, T., 2020. Pelagisk løft - oksidasjon i fryselagret filet produsert fra lakefryst makrell (No. MA 20-08). Møreforskning.
- Lorentzen, G., 1958. Luftfrysing av sild. Undersøkelse av nødvendig frysetid.
- Magnussen, O.M., Hemmingsen, A.K.T., Hardarsson, V., Nordtvedt, T.S., Eikevik, T.M., 2008. Freezing of Fish, in: Evans, J.A. (Ed.), *Frozen Food Science and Technology*. Blackwell Publishing Ltd., Oxford, UK, pp. 151–164. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781444302325.ch7>
- Nordtvedt, T.S., Magnussen, O.M., Hardarsson, V., 2003. Frysing av laksefisk - praktiske erfaringer ved NTNU og SINTEF.
- Norwegian Seafood Council, 2023. Yearly exports from Norway [WWW Document]. *Yrly. Exports Nor.* URL <https://en.seafood.no/market-insight/norwegian-trade/year/> (accessed 12.14.23).
- Østvik, S.O., Grytten, P.K., Gjelseth, L., Aasen, A., Staurset, M., Øy, J., Krogsethagen, T., Valderhaug, H.K., Drønnesund, F., Bøstrand, A., 2018. Utvikling av teknologi og metode for lakefrysing av makrell.PDF.
- Ottestad, S., Enersen, G., Wold, J.P., 2011. Effect of Freezing Temperature on the Color of Frozen Salmon. *J. Food Sci.* 76, S423–S427. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1750-3841.2011.02313.x>
- Stormo, S.K., Martinsen, G., Ageeva, T.N., Tobiassen, T., 2021. Lakefrysing av sjømat (No. 32). NOFIMA.
- Svendsen, E.S., Widell, K.N., Tveit, G.M., Nordtvedt, T.S., Uglem, S., Standal, I., Greiff, K., 2022. Industrial methods of freezing, thawing and subsequent chilled storage of whitefish. *J. Food Eng.* 315. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2021.110803>
- Widell, K.N., 2012. Energy efficiency of freezing tunnels (Doctoral thesis). NTNU.
- Widell, K.N., Eikevik, T.M., Walnum, H.T., 2012. The effect of reduced air fan speed on freezing times and energy consumption in a freezing tunnel. Presented at the 10th IIR Gustav Lorentzen Conference, Delft, Netherlands.
- Widell, K.N., Nordtvedt, T.S., Stavset, O., 2014. Nøkkeltall for kuldeanlegg i pelagisk industri. SINTEF Energi.
- Widell, K.N., Svendsen, E.S., Selvnes, H., Sevault, A., Hafner, A., Nordtvedt, T.S., 2022. Energy flow analysis of an industrial ammonia refrigeration system and potential for a cold thermal energy storage. Presented at the 15th IIR Gustav Lorentzen Conference on Natural Refrigerants, International Institute of Refrigeration (IIR), Trondheim, Norway. <https://doi.org/10.18462/IIR.GL2022.0034>